

A COMBINED THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF PROGRESSIVE FAILURE OF NON-CRIMP 3D ORTHOGONAL WEAVE COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY

A general approach to 3-D progressive failure modelling and strength predictions of textile composites, based on 3-D Mosaic model, is demonstrated on the case of non-crimp 3-D orthogonal woven fabric composites. A combined theoretical-experimental study, performed for one typical E-glass 3D orthogonal non-crimp weave composite, showed excellent agreement between theoretical and experimental results.

Keywords: Textile Composite, 3D Weave, 3-D Analysis, Mechanical Characterization

INTRODUCTION

Computational modeling of progressive failure processes and predictive strength analysis of textile composites gain fast growing scientific interest and practical importance. Having capabilities to accurately predict the damage initiation thresholds and ultimate failure loads under various in-service loading conditions, enables for a significant reduction of expensive and time consuming mechanical characterization work, facilitates the design efficiency and shortens the product development cycle. This paper implements a novel general methodology aimed at computational modeling of progressive failure in textile composites using 3-D Mosaic model approach. The approach is self-consistent and transparent; it can be used within any 3-D finite element analysis framework. It incorporates relatively simple yet mechanistically justifiable material models, discretization schemes, 3-D stress/strain analysis tools, failure mode identification criteria, simple and efficient progressive failure algorithm.

A detailed mathematical description of the basic version of 3-D Mosaic material model and respective 3-D variational analysis approach can be found in [1]. Application of the model and analysis approach to progressive failure modeling and strength predictions of textile composites has been detailed in [2]. Recent modifications of the model and analysis approach, with new capabilities added for progressive failure analysis realization have been presented in [3]. The essential features of this approach are briefly summarized in first part of this paper. Its application is then illustrated on the example of textile composite made of E-glass 3D orthogonal woven non-crimp fabric and

Derakane 8084 epoxy – vinyl ester resin. The analysis is performed at the level of unit cell micromechanics, where the textile composite Unit Cell is treated as an assembly of 3-D unidirectional composites (e.g. resin-impregnated yarns) and 3-D matrix blocks connecting them. Each unidirectional composite is characterized with its individual elastic properties and ultimate strains, assigned for nine independent failure modes (3 in tension, 3 in compression and 3 in shear). Also, specified sets of elastic property “reduction factors” are used for the bricks of unidirectional composites and matrix.

With these capabilities in hand, the developed progressive failure analysis algorithm is used for predictions of the Unit Cell damage initiation thresholds, ultimate strains and stresses under in-plane tensile loading in the warp and fill fiber directions. The obtained theoretical results are compared to experimental data including two damage initiation thresholds (determined by Acoustic Emission method), ultimate failure strains and stresses. Excellent agreement between theoretical and experimental results is observed for both loading cases with the use of initial input data in the analysis. The adjustment of input data by some of experimental results would make the agreement even better.

3-D MOSAIC ANALYSIS APPROACH

The 3-D variational analysis approach called 3-D Mosaic has been originally developed in [4] with the use of arbitrary degree splines as the displacement approximation functions. The approach has been modified in [1], where splines were replaced by Bernstein approximation polynomials of an arbitrary degree serving as the basis functions in all three coordinate directions. A general progressive failure analysis methodology, based on this approach, has been described and illustrated on the example of 3D woven composite in [2]. Recent publication [3] elaborated some new aspects of this approach and illustrated its application on one typical example of non-crimp 3D orthogonal weave composite made of E-glass fiber and Derakane 8084 epoxy-vinyl ester resin. Same material is studied in this work more comprehensively and with the emphasis on comparing the theoretical predictions with experimental data from [5, 6].

First step of 3-D Mosaic analysis approach is illustrated conceptually in Fig. 1 and can be briefly described as follows. Some arbitrary volumetric element of textile composite in the form of a parallelepiped contains three non-penetrating, solid deformable composite yarns, which can be termed as “inclusions”. Each of these inclusions is a homogenized unidirectional composite. The inclusions may be arbitrarily curved, and each of them may have its individual effective elastic and strength properties. The volumetric element in Fig. 1 is shown with three inclusions taking specific positions for illustrative purpose only; it may contain any allowable number of inclusions, and those may take any possible positions. Rest of the volumetric element, which is free of the inclusions, is occupied by a homogeneous matrix material. It is further assumed that the entire centerline and the cross-sectional shape of each inclusion within the volumetric element can be geometrically characterized with respect to the chosen global coordinate system $\{x, y, z\}$. Such a characterization shall be provided by the geometric model in each specific case of textile composite.

Further, Fig. 1 shows how the volumetric element under consideration is discretized into a number of “sub-volumes” by three sets of mutually orthogonal planes. As illustrated in the figure, each sub-volume may contain only matrix material, or matrix material and

one inclusion material, or matrix material and two inclusion materials. In more general cases, a sub-volume may contain matrix and three or more inclusion materials, or be occupied entirely by one inclusion material. within entire textile composite volume has been represented by respective model.

Figure 1. A volumetric element of textile composite (left) with three fragments of different composite yarn inclusions. Same volumetric element after discretization by three sets of mutually orthogonal planes (right); representative sub-volumes extracted.

Obviously, as the number of inclusions within the volumetric element grows, the diversity of sub-volume types grows accordingly. This growing diversity and internal complexity of sub-volumes does not affect the essence of the approach, however it affects the formulation of respective failure criteria. In any case, each of those fragments of different inclusions, contained in different sub-volumes, have to be characterized by their respective physical volumes, orientations with respect to the global coordinate system, and their individual mechanical properties. All such information shall be available after the geometry of each unidirectional composite yarn in the composite has been determined.

The next principal step is to homogenize all individual sub-volumes within initial volumetric element, as illustrated in Fig. 1, in order to obtain a much simpler material model. This means that one, two, etc. unidirectional (generally, curved) composite fragments within each sub-volume are “smeared” with respective matrix material contained within this sub-volume, and the sub-volume is replaced by its homogeneous (generally, non-isotropic) equivalent. After this is performed for all sub-volumes within the original volumetric element, the sub-volume assembly converts into respective 3-D Mosaic structure of the type illustrated in Fig. 2 (the drawings in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 were not aimed to be in exact correspondence). So, the result of this step is that the initial volume of textile composite, which contained some number of curved unidirectional composite yarn inclusions, has been replaced by (in some sense, equivalent) 3-D MOSAIC structure assembled from some number of distinct homogeneous anisotropic

material bricks in the three coordinate directions. If we could establish sufficiently good quantitative correspondence between the two material models (meaning that they should at least provide sufficiently close displacement, strain and stress fields agreement for various types of loading), this step of the analysis development would be successfully accomplished. The principal benefit would be that it is much easier to solve any solid mechanics boundary value problem for a Mosaic structure of the type shown in Fig. 2 than for the original textile composite volume in Fig. 1. In the Mosaic model all details of the individual yarn centerline curvatures, cross-sectional shapes, yarn interlacing in the cross-over regions, etc., do not have to be explicitly addressed.

Figure 2. Generic 3-D Mosaic parallelepiped with the boundaries between different material bricks shown by thick lines and partition into discrete elements by thin lines.

In the third step of this analysis development we introduce three sets of planes, perpendicular to x , y and z coordinate axes, in order to partition the Mosaic parallelepiped of Fig. 2 (left) into some number of computational parallelepipeds (called here “discrete elements”) shown in Fig. 2 (right). Such partitioning can be uniform within each material brick interval or it can be arbitrarily nonuniform. After that, each homogeneous material brick can be viewed as an assembly of some number of discrete elements in x , y and z directions. Each discrete element in the Mosaic parallelepiped is automatically assigned mechanical properties of that material brick which it is part of.

Due to the location and count of discretization planes in Fig. 3 is chosen by the analyst, each material brick can be meshed finer and finer by increasing the number of partition planes in each direction. Also worth mentioning that the number of partition planes within each interval (x_1, x_2) , (x_2, x_3) , ..., (x_L, x_{L+1}) in x -direction, (y_1, y_2) , (y_2, y_3) , ..., (y_M, y_{M+1}) in y -direction and (z_1, z_2) , (z_2, z_3) , ..., (z_L, z_{L+1}) in z -direction is chosen independently.

After the partition of 3-D Mosaic structure has been performed, a 3-D displacement field is represented, for each individual discrete element (we assign subscript q to it), in the following form of triple series with the products of separated basis functions:

$$u_{\alpha}^{(q)}(x, y, z) = \sum_{i=0}^{I_q} \sum_{j=0}^{J_q} \sum_{k=0}^{K_q} U_{ijk}^{\alpha, q} X_i(x) Y_j(y) Z_k(z); \quad \alpha = 1, 2, 3 \quad (1)$$

Here, integers I_q , J_q and K_q define the number of degrees of freedom (d.o.f.) assigned to each discrete element in the mosaic parallelepiped; $U_{ijk}^{\alpha, q}$ are undetermined

coefficients; $X_i(x)$, $Y_j(y)$ and $Z_k(z)$ are three sets of basis functions, which are assumed here identical for all of the discrete elements.

In this analysis approach, Bernstein approximation polynomials of arbitrary degree serve as the basis functions in (1). Further mathematical and computational aspects of the variational analysis development can be found in [1-3]. After all of the coefficients $U_{ijk}^{\alpha,q}$ entering in (1) have been determined, the 3-D displacement field is computed point-wise by direct series summation in (1) for any given triad of coordinates x , y and z . After that, the 3-D strain field is computed by substituting the displacement series (1) into equations of 3-D linear elasticity relating strains and displacements and point-wise summation of the obtained triple series. After that, the 3-D stress field is computed by substituting the triple series for strains into constitutive equations of linear anisotropic elasticity and the point-wise summation of the obtained triple series for stresses. Note that all numerical values of the displacements, strains and stresses in the Mosaic structure are obtained directly from their respective triple series, without extrapolations to the Gaussian points or similar post-processing procedures commonly used in finite element analysis.

PROGRESSIVE FAILURE ANALYSIS USING 3-D MOSAIC MODEL

Now, having the capability of computing 3-D displacement, strain and stress fields at any point of 3-D Mosaic structure, including interfaces between distinct material bricks, we can proceed to the development of progressive failure algorithm. This development is entirely within the framework of Continuum Damage Mechanics methodology. The approach includes identification of possible failure modes (which depend on the nature of each brick material), selection of appropriate phenomenological failure criterion for each failure mode and type of loading (e.g., tension, compression or shear), and specific scheme of a gradual elastic property reduction. One variant of such progressive failure analysis methodology has been described in [2]. Here we follow that methodology with some minor modifications which will be notified later.

A progressive failure analysis algorithm can be based on the material brick assembly (see Fig. 2 left), considering each brick as a primary entity of the analysis. In this case, within each cycle of progressive failure analysis, the adopted failure criteria have to be applied to individual material bricks. After each sequential failure occurrence, depending on the realized failure mode, respective elastic properties of the failed brick have to be replaced by some “reduced” properties. The property reduction is performed via specific “reduction factors”. Each material brick can experience only one failure occurrence corresponding to each failure mode. In the subsequent cycles of progressive failure analysis, the previously realized failure modes in all of the material bricks are excluded from consideration. Note that after each failure occurrence, all of the bricks in the Mosaic structure remain homogeneous. This is the simplest approach, which is fully consistent with the underlying 3-D Mosaic concept. However, in practical terms it may appear not accurate enough, if the primary textile composite partition into the bricks (refer to Fig. 1) was not sufficiently fine. Accordingly, the progressive failure analysis results may strongly depend on how good the initial discretization of the composite into material bricks was.

A more sophisticated, though also more complicated, approach is to perform progressive failure analysis at the level of discrete elements, i.e., to relate it to the secondarily partitioned structure (see Fig. 2 right). In this case, the failure criteria have to be applied to each individual discrete element, and after each consecutive failure occurrence the discrete element properties have to be replaced by respective “reduced” properties. In this scheme, each discrete element can experience one failure from each possible failure mode. This progressive failure analysis approach would be most natural in the framework of conventional finite element analysis.

In the analysis approach used here, the occurrence of each failure event is determined by a simple and mechanistically validated maximum strain failure criterion. Accordingly, nine possible failure modes (tension in directions 1, 2, 3; compression in direction 1, 2, 3; shear in planes 2-3, 1-3, 1-2) of each brick can be realized. If necessary, any other suitable phenomenological failure criterion can be incorporated into the developed progressive failure analysis algorithm and computer code without any difficulty.

A complete reduction scheme applied to the elastic characteristics of unidirectional composite yarn bricks and matrix bricks can be found in Table 1 of [2] with corrections made in [3]. Those corrections concern Poisson’s ratios only: the “reduction rule” for them under tension in direction 1, for example, is according to [2]:

$$\tilde{\nu}_{21}^{(q)} = \nu_{21}^{(q)} / \alpha_1^{(q)} \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\nu}_{31}^{(q)} = \nu_{31}^{(q)} / \alpha_1^{(q)} \quad (2)$$

while the following have been suggested in [3] and implemented in the current version of 3D MOSAIC computer code:

$$\tilde{\nu}_{12}^{(q)} = \nu_{12}^{(q)} \alpha_1^{(q)} \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\nu}_{13}^{(q)} = \nu_{13}^{(q)} \alpha_1^{(q)} \quad (3)$$

Analogous corrections have been made for the Poisson’s ratios in other loading cases. The above corrections were made after numerical simulations of progressive failure problems for unidirectional composites and isotropic matrix (note that initially isotropic matrix material becomes non-isotropic after its first failure occurrence). The readership is directed to publications [2] and [3] for further details of the developed progressive failure algorithm.

COMPUTATIONAL MODEL AND INPUT DATA

To illustrate the developed progressive failure analysis approach, we consider here a representative example of 3D orthogonal woven composite reinforced with a 3.25 kg/m² areal density E-glass fabric and consolidated with Derakane 8084 epoxy-vinyl ester resin. This fabric is one of 3TEX’s most popular commercial products. Due to a high commercial interest in this particular textile composite product, theoretical predictions of its mechanical properties, especially strength characteristics, have significant practical value.

Fig. 3 shows geometric model of the Unit Cell constructed by 3TEX for the 3D woven fabric preform (left) and its respective 3-D Mosaic model (right). The composite Unit Cell model contains seven different materials; four of them are assumed to be identical unidirectional transversely isotropic composites oriented in warp, fill, Z-along z -coordinate, and Z-along x -coordinate directions. The other two distinct materials, which

are monoclinic in the global coordinate system x, y, z , were obtained from the inclined segments of Z yarn (the curved segments are seen in the fabric model) by smearing them with certain surrounding volumes of the matrix material. The rest of the Unit Cell volume is occupied by many bricks of pure matrix having very different dimensions. In this 3-D Mosaic model, there are 9 material bricks in x -direction, 5 in y -direction, and 11 in z ; 495 material bricks total. Even if progressive failure analysis is performed at the level of material bricks, the maximum possible failure occurrences would be 4455.

Figure 3. Unit Cell geometry model of the 3D orthogonal woven non-crimp fabric (left) and its respective 3-D Mosaic model used in analysis (right).

The Unit Cell dimensions adopted for the Mosaic model in Fig. 3 are noted as $2a$ in x , $2b$ in y and $2c$ in z . Their numerical values used in the analysis are as follows:

$$2a = 7.580mm, 2b = 7.258mm, 2c = 2.602mm \quad (4)$$

The following lengths of intervals a_i in x , b_i in y , and c_i in z , associated with the material bricks, were used (the intervals are numbered from left to right, from front to back, and from bottom to top):

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 = 1.58mm, a_2 = 0.11mm, a_3 = 0.41mm, a_4 = 0.11mm, a_5 = 3.16mm, \\ a_6 = 0.11mm, a_7 = 0.41mm, a_8 = 0.11mm, a_9 = 1.58mm, b_1 = 0.202mm, \\ b_2 = 3.225mm, b_3 = 0.404mm, b_4 = 3.225mm, b_5 = 0.202mm, c_1 = 0.207mm, \\ c_2 = 0.145mm, c_3 = 0.145mm, c_4 = 0.429mm, c_5 = 0.271mm, c_6 = 0.208mm, \\ c_7 = 0.271mm, c_8 = 0.429mm, c_9 = 0.145mm, c_{10} = 0.145mm, c_{11} = 0.207mm \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Assuming that uniformly distributed displacement u_x^0 is applied at both ends of the Unit Cell, the boundary conditions imposed under x -directional (warp) loading are:

$$u_x = u_x^0 \text{ at } x = 0 \text{ and } x = 2a \quad (6)$$

Analogous boundary condition are imposed in the y -directional (fill) loading case.

Initial, “undamaged” elastic characteristics of the materials incorporated in the Unit Cell model were taken as following. For the matrix material:

$$E_m = 2.90GPa, \nu_m = 0.35, G_m = 1.07GPa \quad (7)$$

For the warp, fill and Z unidirectional composites in their local coordinate system (properties were evaluated by Orientational Averaging Method):

$$E_1 = 48.1GPa, E_2 = E_3 = 11.0GPa, G_{12} = G_{13} = 4.30GPa, G_{23} = 3.80GPa, \\ \nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.315, \quad \nu_{23} = 0.445 \quad (8)$$

The other principal set of input data includes ultimate strains of all involved materials in tension, compression and shear. These characteristics were mainly obtained from the manufacturer's data sheets and from available literature data for unidirectional E-glass/epoxy composites. In the following, superscripts "T", "C" and "S" correspond to tension, compression and shear failure modes, respectively. Ultimate strains of matrix material were taken as follows:

$$\varepsilon_1^T = \varepsilon_2^T = \varepsilon_3^T = 2.0\%, \varepsilon_1^C = \varepsilon_2^C = \varepsilon_3^C = 2.5\%, \varepsilon_4^S = \varepsilon_5^S = \varepsilon_6^S = 4\% \quad (9)$$

and ultimate strains of the unidirectional composites were taken as:

$$\varepsilon_1^T = 3.0\%, \varepsilon_2^T = \varepsilon_3^T = 0.6\%, \varepsilon_1^C = 1.6\%, \varepsilon_2^C = \varepsilon_3^C = 1.5\%, \varepsilon_{23}^S = 2.0\%, \\ \varepsilon_{12}^S = \varepsilon_{13}^S = 2.0\% \quad (10)$$

Another important set of input data are the "reduction factors"; they have to be applied to Young's moduli, Poisson's ratios and shear moduli of the unidirectional composite and matrix materials, see Table 1 in [2] and Table 1 in [3]. Blindly, all of them were initially taken 0.1; this resulted in surprisingly good agreement with experimental data.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

After initial runs of the code for the full Unit Cell Mosaic model of Fig. 3 it became obvious that going through entire progressive failure process would be problematic. Running one cycle of analysis for the full Unit Cell model took several hours. Assuming that the full run of progressive failure analysis would likely require several hundreds of cycles, the total solution time would count in hundreds of hours, i.e., in weeks of continuous computer run. Based on these estimates, it was decided to simplify the computational model without losing its essential features. Obviously, the first resource is using close-to-symmetry conditions with respect to the planes passing through the center of the Unit Cell and perpendicular to x , y and z axes. This results in the Mosaic model of $1/8^{\text{th}}$ of Unit Cell shown in Fig. 4 (left). This model contains 5 material bricks in x , 3 in y and 5 in z ; 75 total. If using meshing of each material brick into 8 discrete elements, total number of discrete elements would be 600. Each analysis run with second degree Bernstein basis functions takes in this case about 20 minutes. Considering possible 100-200 failure events till ultimate failure, the full computation with this model would still require 30-60 hours of continuous computer run.

Further simplification of the $1/8^{\text{th}}$ Unit Cell model is shown in Fig. 4 (right). In this case, Z-yarn is modeled as a zig-zag, with its segment seen in the figure having a Γ -shape. The "transitional", corner brick represents in the simplest possible way the curved part of Z yarn, where it turns from the vertical (z) to the horizontal (x) orientation. It was assumed that material of this brick is also a unidirectional composite, having same fiber volume fraction, but rotated at 45° angle about y -axis. In this case the 3-D Mosaic model contains 3 material bricks in x , 3 in y and 5 in z ; their total number is reduced to 45, and the maximum possible number of failure events goes down to 360. If meshing each material brick into 8 discrete elements and using second degree Bernstein

basis functions, one cycle of analysis takes only 7 minutes. Hence, the computation till ultimate failure can be performed in less than 10 hours of continuous computer run.

Figure 4. 3-D Mosaic model of the original 1/8th Unit Cell (left) and simplified 1/8th Unit Cell (right).

COMPARISON OF THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Tensile testing of standard coupons cut in the warp and fill directions of the 3D woven composite were supplemented by acoustic emission data providing damage initiation thresholds, progressive cracks observation at different load levels, and full-field surface strain mapping, as described in [5,6]. The obtained acoustic emission data were used for validating 3-D Mosaic model predictions of the first and second damage thresholds. The comparisons of theoretical and experimental results are summarized in Table 1 and Fig. 5. As Table 1 shows, the obtained theoretical and experimental damage initiation characteristics are in a very good agreement for both warp and fill loading directions. Particularly remarkable is that in the warp-loading case the predicted damage initiation strain is right in the middle between the experimental damage initiation strain and first damage threshold. Especially close agreement is observed for the second damage thresholds in both loading cases. The ultimate failure strains are underpredicted in both loading cases (though very slightly for warp loading), while the ultimate failure stresses are overpredicted in both cases (again, the agreement is closer for warp loading). Fig. 5 illustrates that for both loading cases the predicted stress-strain curve fits well among three experimental curves in this case.

Table 1. Theoretical and experimental [5, 6] damage initiation and ultimate failure characteristics of the 3D woven composite for warp- and fill-directional loading cases.

Damage Initiation and Failure Characteristics	Warp-loading			Fill-loading		
	Theory	Experiment	Δ , %	Theory	Experiment	Δ , %
Damage initiation strain, %		0.26±0.11			0.16±0.05	
First damage threshold, %	0.325	0.43±0.04	24.4	0.458	0.37±0.06	-24.8
Second damage threshold, %	0.560	0.54±0.04	-3.7	0.602	0.59±0.04	-2.0
Ultimate strain, %	2.67	2.74±0.29	2.6	2.86	3.33±0.27	14.1
Ultimate stress, MPa	461	429±34	-7.5	555	486±5	14.2

Figure 5. Theoretical (red) and experimental (blue-green, 3 samples in each case) stress-strain curves for warp- (left) and fill- (right) directional tensile loading of non-crimp 3D orthogonal weave composite.

CONCLUSIONS

The initial validation of progressive failure analysis approach, based on 3-D Mosaic model, have been performed using tensile test data and acoustic emission monitoring. With initially assumed input data for all materials in the model, without any calibration by experimental data, the predicted damage initiation thresholds, ultimate strains and ultimate stresses are in a close agreement with experimental results. For some characteristics the agreement is within 2-4%, while even in the worst cases the deviation is less than 25%. The analysis will be further exercised for other textile composites and loading cases with continuing support of experimental studies.

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